

AGE-RELATED ASPECTS OF OSTEOARTHRITIS IN WOMEN

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Annotation. Osteoarthritis (OA) is becoming one of the most common diseases of modern society, affecting more than 20% of the world's population over the age of 50, and the number of patients with OA is constantly growing, which is associated with an increase in life expectancy. Generally, etiology of OA is multifactorial and includes both constitutional (old age, gender, obesity, heredity, state of reproductive function) and mechanical factors. The results of sample studies conducted in Uzbekistan suggest that currently at least 30% of the working-age population of our country is overweight and 25% is obese. A steady increase in obesity is observed in almost all countries of the world: over the past 10 years, its prevalence in the world has increased by an average of 75%. However, despite the high prevalence, the effect of abdominal obesity on the course of OA in women has not been studied. The disease is based on genetic, endocrine causes, irrational overloads, and obesity. Late diagnosis and ineffective therapy lead to a decrease in the quality of life of patients with OA, an increase in temporary disability and early disability of people of working age.

The purpose of the research was conducting an anthropometric and somatometric examination and establishing body types in women with osteoarthritis in the age aspect.

Materials and methods of research. We examined 122 women with OA of large and small joints. Patients were divided into two groups. Women of the mature age (40-60 years) 27% and elderly women (from 61 to 74 years) 73%. The control group consisted of 40 women aged 45-65 years without OA. The results of the research. All anthropometric indicators were processed by the method of variational statistics using the interactive SOMA software package and the Statistic 7.0 application software package. Calculations of the average statistical value (M), the standard deviation from the average (δ), the error of the average (m) were carried out. The reliability of the intergroup differences of the studied features was assessed using the Student-Fisher t -criterion and χ^2 .

The results. The analysis of somatometric data showed that women with OA were statistically significantly more likely to have lower

height, greater body weight, BMI, more fat and bone mass against the background of lower values of muscle mass compared to women of the same age population. In women with OA, the decrease in the proportion of muscle mass in the soma reached almost 10%. In addition, with abdominal type of obesity, damage to a larger number of joints, more pronounced X-ray changes and functional disorders were observed. Among the examined women, a megalosomal constitution was detected in 83% of cases, a mesosomal constitution was registered in 15% of cases and a leptosomal constitution was practically not detected. The megalosomal constitution is characterized by high height, increased body weight, strong development of musculature and bone tissue, as well as pronounced development of adipose tissue. These women are overweight and obese, which is an additional risk factor in the development and progression of OA.

In conclusion somatotyping allowed us to establish that the majority of the studied women with OA had a megalosomal constitution and among them there were practically no women with a leptosomal constitution. In the age aspect, it was indicated that older women had statistically significantly higher indicators of height, body weight and BMI compared with women of mature age.

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